

Characterisation of γ -Al₂O₃-supported Pd catalysts by X-ray diffraction, temperature programmed reduction, thermal analysis and catalytic probe^ψ

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Alumina-supported 2% and 5% (by mass) Pd monometallic catalysts have been prepared by the impregnation method. The catalysts were characterised by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), temperature programmed reduction (TPR), hydrogen chemisorption measurements and thermal analysis. CO oxidation was used as a probe to compare the performance of all the catalysts prepared. 5% Pd catalysts are found to be more active than their 2% analogues. The catalysts prepared using two different precursors viz. palladium nitrate and palladium acetylacetonate showed very similar activity profiles. The effects of microwave radiation and calcination on the properties of the catalysts prepared were also studied. Microwave radiation did not affect the properties of the catalysts significantly.

For both practical and fundamental reasons, the heterogeneous catalytic oxidation of carbon monoxide has received much attention recently. The CO oxidation catalysts are often an integral component of pollution control devices designed to reduce industrial and automotive emissions¹. Apart from catalytic converters, air purification devices and CO gas sensors also employ CO oxidation catalysts. Recently, CO oxidation has also been utilized in closed-cycle CO₂ lasers². Furthermore, the relative simplicity of the CO oxidation reaction on a metal surface makes it an ideal model system of a heterogeneous catalytic process, a process involving molecular and dissociative (atomic) adsorption, surface reaction, and desorption of products. The removal of CO as CO₂ from an automotive exhaust is accomplished by a catalytic converter utilizing the supported noble metals, Pt, Pd and Rh³⁻⁵. This has led to numerous recent studies of the kinetics of this reaction on supported metal catalysts^{6,7} and transient kinetic studies on polycrystalline foils^{8,9}, which have sought to identify and quantify the parameters of the elementary mechanistic steps in CO oxidation. In general, CO oxidation reaction is found to follow the Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism¹⁰.

Apart from the higher specific activities, noble metals are preferred because they are less liable to sulphur poisoning than metal oxide catalysts¹¹. Pt and Pd catalysts

are most commonly used for total oxidation¹². The oxides of Pt and Pd formed during the reactions are less volatile as compared to RuO₂, OsO₄ and Ir₂O₃ which are also toxic¹³. Other noble metals such as Au and Ag are not suitable for high temperature and high space velocity applications.

Pd-containing catalysts have been widely studied; in particular, Pd supported on Al₂O₃ has been reported to be very active in combustion reactions¹⁴. The activity is influenced by many factors such as the calcination temperature, Pd particle size, the role of lattice oxygen, Pd loading and the reaction conditions. Use of microwave radiation has been shown to improve the turn over numbers during the hydrogenation of benzene on Pd supported on alumina and silica¹⁵.

This study presents the results of comparative characterization studies on 2% and 5% (by mass) Pd supported on Al₂O₃ catalysts. The aim of this investigation was to study the effects of Pd loading, and of various treatments such as calcination, and exposure to microwave radiation on the properties of the catalysts prepared using two different precursors viz. palladium nitrate (Pd(NO₃)₂) and palladium acetylacetonate (Pd(acac)₂). The prepared catalysts were then evaluated by performing activity experiments in a fixed-bed catalytic reactor by using oxidation of CO in air as a model reaction.

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

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Results and discussion

(a) Characterisation of the catalysts :

The catalysts prepared in this study were characterised by using X-ray diffraction (XRD), chemisorption studies, temperature programmed reduction (TPR) and thermogravimetric analysis – differential scanning calorimetry (TGA-DSC) techniques.

POWDER X-RAY DIFFRACTION (XRD) :

XRD patterns for the catalysts dried at 110°C :

The XRD patterns of the 2% and 5% Pd by mass, prepared by the incipient wetness technique, and dried in an oven at 110°C for several hours, showed the presence of alumina but no indication for palladium or any of its oxides (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. XRD patterns for systems dried at 110°C.

The crystalline phases were identified by the comparison of the XRD patterns of the catalysts with the Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS) file data or other reports¹⁵. Fig. 1 shows the broad nature of the peaks corresponding to poor crystalline nature of alumina support. The XRD pattern for metallic Pd has peaks at positions very similar to γ - Al_2O_3 . This makes unequivocal identification of metallic Pd in the presence of Al_2O_3 difficult.

XRD patterns for the catalysts treated with microwaves for 5 min :

The XRD patterns for 2% by mass Pd/ Al_2O_3 catalysts prepared from a nitrate (Fig. 2a) and acetylacetonate (Fig. 4a) precursor and irradiated with microwaves for 5 min, did not show any peaks corresponding to Pd or PdO_x as was expected. However, in the case of 5% Pd/ Al_2O_3 catalysts prepared by using the nitrate precursor (Fig. 3a) and irradiated with microwaves for 5 min, a distinct peak for PdO_x was observed; whereas there was still no indication of Pd or PdO_x when catalyst prepared using the acetylacetonate precursor was studied (Fig. 5a). This indicates that microwave radiation does not decompose the acetylacetonate precursor completely and palladium being still present in its original form on the support.

Fig. 2. XRD pattern for 2% Pd/ Al_2O_3 catalysts prepared using nitrate precursor [$*\text{PdO}_x + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$].

Fig. 3. XRD pattern for 5% Pd/ Al_2O_3 catalysts prepared using nitrate precursor [$*\text{PdO}_x + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$].

Fig. 4. XRD pattern for 2% Pd/ Al_2O_3 catalysts prepared using acac precursor [$\text{PdO}_x + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$].

Fig. 5. XRD pattern for 5% Pd/ Al_2O_3 catalysts prepared using acac precursor [$\text{PdO}_x + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$].

XRD patterns for the catalysts calcined at 450°C for 5 h :

After calcining 5% Pd/ Al_2O_3 catalysts at 450°C for 5 h, a peak at $\sim 34^\circ$ corresponding to PdO_x is observed (Figs. 2b-5b). The presence of this peak indicated that the complete decomposition of the precursors and the formation of PdO_x have taken place. However, poorly crystalline alumina also gave signal in the same region; as a result it was difficult to distinguish between the contributions of the two systems. A small and broad peak was also observed in case of catalysts (2% by mass Pd).

XRD patterns for the catalysts irradiated with microwaves after calcination :

When the catalysts were treated with microwave radiation for 5 min after calcination at 450°C for 5 h, the XRD patterns looked the same as those for the catalysts which have only been calcined, indicating that micro-

wave radiation does not cause changes detectable by XRD (Figs. 2c-5c).

Determination of metal dispersion by chemisorption :

Table 1 shows the hydrogen chemisorption results obtained by the volumetric method.

Table 1. Dispersion values for various Pd catalysts

Catalyst	Pre-treatment	Dispersion ^a
2% (by mass) :		
$\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	MW-5 min	34
$\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	Calcined	32
$\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	Calcined, MW-5 min	37
$\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2$	MW-5 min	14
$\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2$	Calcined	43
$\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2$	Calcined, MW-5 min	30
5% (by mass) :		
$\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	MW-5 min	14
$\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	Calcined	18
$\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	Calcined, MW-5 min	20
$\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2$	MW-5 min	11
$\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2$	Calcined	24
$\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2$	Calcined, MW-5 min	17

^aFraction of metal atoms on the surface of the catalyst.

Effect of loading on metal dispersion :

The metal dispersion was found to decrease with an increase in the Pd loading i.e. from 2% to 5% in the present study.

Effect of precursor on metal dispersion :

When the nitrate precursor was used for the catalyst preparation, the metal dispersion in both, 2% and 5% systems were found to be very similar irrespective of the kind of mild treatment given to the catalysts. However, a very slight increase in dispersion was observed when catalysts were treated with microwave radiation after calcination at 450°C for 5 h.

In the case of catalysts prepared using $\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2$, an irregular trend in dispersion values was observed. The range of metal dispersion varied from 14–43% in this case. After exposing both the catalysts (2% and 5%) to microwaves, dispersion of Pd in the catalyst was found to be poor (14 and 11 for 2% and 5% respectively). However, after calcining the catalysts at 450°C for 5 h yielded better dispersion compared to their nitrate analogues e.g. 43 compared to 32 in case of 2% systems and 24 compared to 18 in case of 5% systems. Treating the calcined samples further with microwaves causes a decrease in the

dispersion suggesting that sintering might have occurred.

TEMPERATURE PROGRAMMED REDUCTION :

Due to the hydrogen adsorption ability of palladium, quantitative comparisons of the amounts of hydrogen consumed in TPR experiments is not helpful in determining the state of reduction of palladium. However, an approximate inference of reduction temperatures can be made or it could be attributed to the presence of β -palladium hydride (β -PdH) phase. TPR profiles for the catalysts show the reduction peaks listed in Table 2.

Table 2. TPR data for various Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts

Sample	Peak positions (in °C)		
	I	II	III
Fig. 6 :			
2% Pd(NO ₃) ₂ (MW)	84	108	132
2% Pd(NO ₃) ₂ (calcined)	97(-ve)		
2% Pd(NO ₃) ₂ (calcined, MW)	104	116	649
Fig. 7 :			
5% Pd(NO ₃) ₂ (MW)	123	146	
5% Pd(NO ₃) ₂ (calcined)	99(-ve)	112	879
5% Pd(NO ₃) ₂ (calcined, MW)	93(-ve)	840	840
Fig. 8 :			
2% Pd(acac) ₂ (MW)	159	247	392
2% Pd(acac) ₂ (calcined)	95(-ve)	846	
2% Pd(acac) ₂ (calcined, MW)	90(-ve)		
Fig. 9 :			
5% Pd(acac) ₂ (MW)	138	244	379
5% Pd(acac) ₂ (calcined)	93(-ve)	419	
5% Pd(acac) ₂ (calcined, MW)	99(-ve)	846	

It should be noted that the Pd on the alumina support is oxidized to PdO_x after calcination at 450°C for 5 h. However this PdO_x formed, is reduced to β -palladium hydride when the TPR apparatus is flushed with the H₂/N₂ mixture at room temperature before the start of each experiment. This reduction is sometimes very facile and has been observed at temperatures as low as ca. 270 K²⁰. However, in the present study palladium oxide was found to be reduced at temperatures below 200°C (Figs. 6a and 7a). The inverted peak in case of calcined samples can be related to desorption of hydrogen resulting from the decomposition of β -palladium hydride²¹ (Figs. 6b and 7b).

In the case of the catalysts prepared by using palladium acetylacetonate as a precursor, three reduction peaks were observed for the catalysts treated with microwave radiation for 5 min (Figs. 8a and 9a), probably indicating

Fig. 6. TPR profile for 2% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using nitrate precursor.

Fig. 7. TPR profile for 5% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using nitrate precursor.

Fig. 8. TPR profile for 2% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using acetylacetonate precursor.

the palladium species formed during microwave heating is different in character from the one obtained after calcination (Figs. 8b and 9b).

Fig. 9. TPR profile for 5% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using acetylacetonate precursor.

THERMAL ANALYSIS (TGA-DSC) :

Thermograms of the catalysts prepared using nitrate precursor showed weight loss only due to the loss of the moisture from the surface of the catalyst (Figs. 10 and 11). This observation was supported by the peaks in the TPR profiles for the corresponding catalyst. No phase changes were observed in any of these catalysts.

Fig. 10. TGA-DSC profile for 2% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using nitrate precursor.

Fig. 11. TGA-DSC profile for 5% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using nitrate precursor.

However, the peaks at $\sim 200^\circ\text{C}$ in thermograms for the catalysts prepared using the acetylacetonate precursor and irradiated with microwave radiation only are due to precursor decomposition (Figs. 12 and 13). This is consistent with the peaks observed in TPR profile for the

Fig. 12. TGA-DSC profile for 2% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using acetylacetonate precursor.

Fig. 13. TGA-DSC profile for 5% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using acetylacetonate precursor.

same catalysts and confirms that the acetylacetonate precursor is not completely decomposed by the microwave radiation. The catalysts after being calcined and also those exposed to microwaves after calcination showed some weight loss at temperature around 100°C, which could be due to the loss of surface moisture.

(b) Catalytic activity towards CO oxidation :

Figs. 14–17 show the amount of CO that has been oxidised in the gas feed as a function of temperature over the above mentioned catalysts. The results of the experiment are summarised in Table 3.

The decrease in light-off temperature was observed

Fig. 14. CO oxidation profile for 2% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using nitrate precursor.

Fig. 15. CO oxidation profile for 2% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using acetylacetonate precursor.

Fig. 16. CO oxidation profile for 5% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using nitrate precursor.

Fig. 17. CO oxidation profile for 5% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts prepared using acetylacetonate precursor.

Table 3. CO oxidation data for various Pd catalysts

Fig. No.	Catalyst	Treatment given	Light-off temperature ^a /°C
2% (by mass) :			
14	Pd(NO ₃) ₂	MW-5 min	136
	Pd(NO ₃) ₂	Calcined	133
	Pd(NO ₃) ₂	Calcined + MW-5 min	110
15	Pd(acac) ₂	Calcined	122
	Pd(acac) ₂	Calcined + MW-5 min	127
5% (by mass) :			
16	Pd(NO ₃) ₂	MW-5 min	129
	Pd(NO ₃) ₂	Calcined	92
	Pd(NO ₃) ₂	Calcined + MW-5 min	97
17	Pd(acac) ₂	Calcined	96
	Pd(acac) ₂	Calcined + MW-5 min	104

^aTemperature corresponding to 50% conversion of CO to CO₂.

over calcined catalysts compared to the ones that have been treated with microwaves only. This could be explained in terms of surface PdO_x being formed as a result of calcination at 450°C. This oxide so formed was able to provide activated oxygen to take part in the CO oxidation reaction leading to better CO conversion rates at lower temperatures compared to the systems that were not calcined.

Catalysts containing higher Pd content (5%) were found to be more active than their lower (2%) analogues, irrespective of the treatment given to the catalysts. This suggests that the CO oxidation is a function of amount of Pd species in the catalyst. Data in Table 1 shows that 2% Pd systems have better metal dispersion than their 5% analogues. The performance of the catalysts studied does not seem to fit the general observation that higher dispersion, generally, translates into higher activity. Detailed TEM studies will be able to offer us a better explanation, possibly, in terms of metal particle-size distribution in the catalysts.

A slight increase in the light-off temperature (hence loss in activity) was observed for the catalysts that were calcined at 450°C for 5 h and irradiated with microwaves. This loss in activity can be attributed to sintering of the metal particles.

Experimental

Materials used :

- Palladium nitrate (Pd(NO₃)₂) – supplied by Alfa.
- Palladium acetylacetonate (Pd(acac)₂) – supplied by Johnson Matthey, UK.

- γ -Al₂O₃ was supplied by AKZO (CK 300).

Several catalysts having different palladium loading (2% and 5% by mass) on alumina support were prepared using two different metal precursors :

- Palladium nitrate
- Palladium acetylacetonate

The support, γ -Al₂O₃ was received in the form of cylindrical pellets. The γ -alumina pellets were crushed and sieved to a grain size of 250–500 μ m range.

PREPARATION OF CATALYSTS :

(a) 2% (by mass) Pd supported on alumina using Pd(NO₃)₂ :

About 1 cm³ of Pd(NO₃)₂ solution (assay = 8.39%) and ~6.5 mL of de-ionised water were taken in a small beaker and stirred well. About 5 g of alumina powder were added to the solution and mixed well for few minutes. The pH of the resulting mixture was in the range 5–6. The mixture was left in air to dry for a few hours and then kept in oven at 110°C for drying.

(b) 2% (by mass) Pd supported on alumina using Pd(acac)₂ :

About 0.3 g of Pd(acac)₂ was weighed and dissolved in slight excess of toluene. To this solution about 5 g of alumina powder was added and the mixture was stirred for a few minutes. The pH of the mixture was found to be nearly 7. The mixture was then placed in an oven at 110°C for a few hours for drying.

(c) 5% (by mass) Pd supported on alumina using Pd(NO₃)₂ :

About 2.8 cm³ of Pd(NO₃)₂ solution (assay = 8.39%) and ~6.5 mL of de-ionised water were taken in a small beaker and stirred well. About 5 g of alumina powder were added to the solution and mixed well for a few minutes. The pH of the resulting mixture was in the range 5–6. The mixture was left in air to dry for a few hours and then kept in oven at 110°C for drying.

(d) 5% (by mass) Pd supported on alumina using Pd(acac)₂ :

About 0.75 g of Pd(acac)₂ was weighed and dissolved in slight excess of toluene. To this solution about 5 g of alumina powder was added and the mixture was stirred for few minutes. The pH of the mixture was found to be nearly 7. The mixture was then placed in an oven at 110°C for few hours for drying.

PRE-TREATMENT :

All catalysts, after drying in oven for a few hours were transferred to the sample bottles. From the series

prepared using $\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, about one-third portion of the sample was taken and irradiated in a microwave oven (CEM Corporation, USA) at 100% power for 5 min (denoted MW). Rest of the sample was calcined in a furnace at 450°C for 5 h. After allowing the sample to cool down to room temperature, about half of the sample was taken and again irradiated in a microwave oven at 100% power for 5 min. All samples so prepared were kept in separate bottles and labelled appropriately.

Powder X-ray diffraction :

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the fresh catalysts were recorded using a Siemens Diffractometer D5000. All samples were scanned from $10^\circ < 2\theta < 70^\circ$ using a Cu-K_α radiation source. The use of X-ray diffraction as a structural technique has been described in standard textbooks¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Determination of metal dispersion by chemisorption :

The chemical adsorption of hydrogen was carried out in a conventional volumetric apparatus. About 0.1 g of the catalyst was loaded into a calibrated sample holder. This sample holder was attached to the vacuum line through a sinter and the sample was then out-gassed by heating at 250°C using the home made furnace for half an hour and allowed to come to room temperature. Then the catalyst was reduced in hydrogen at 350°C at a pressure 750 mbar for 30 min. After the reduction, the catalyst was out-gassed at 350°C for about 30 min. The furnace was then removed and out-gassing was still continued while the sample cooled down. The isotherm data was collected by introducing a certain volume of hydrogen into calibrated dosing volume and noting the pressure as dosing pressure. The pressure was allowed to equilibrate. Details regarding the apparatus set-up and volume calibrations are given elsewhere¹⁹. For this experiment, typically 7 or 8 data points were collected in the pressure range of 1–12 mbar at room temperature.

Temperature programmed reduction :

The TPR set-up was assembled using a gas chromatograph (Varian Model 3700 GAS) operating at ~60°C and a Carbolite furnace controlled by a Eurotherm model 818 temperature programmer. The Pico Data Logger software (Pico Technology Ltd.) was used to collect and process the data. Approximately 0.1 g of the catalyst was placed on a quartz wool plug inside a silica tube. The tube was placed in the furnace and the program was set on the controller for the run between 30–850°C. The catalyst was purged with nitrogen for about 20 min in order to remove any air in the system. A reduction mix-

ture containing 10% H_2 in N_2 was used for the experiments. This mixture was passed through the reference arm of the thermal conductivity detector (TCD) of the gas chromatograph (GC), then through the catalytic cell to the sampling arm of the TCD. Once the gas has passed over the solid catalyst, any water formed as a result of the reduction process was removed by the use of a small column of dry silica beads. The system was monitored until the TCD display gave a stabilised reading. Once the stable reading was observed the computer controlled data collection program was started. Heating rate was maintained at 10°C min^{-1} . The change in hydrogen concentration as a function of temperature was recorded.

Thermal analysis (TGA-DSC) :

The TGA/DSC data were collected on a Rheometric Scientific Simultaneous Thermal Analyzer (STA). The sample and the reference (empty) crucibles (both made of alumina) were calibrated under the experimental conditions such as air (zero grade) flowing at a fixed flow rate of ca. 50 $\text{cm}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$ and the baseline was set. About 5–10 mg of the sample was placed into a tared sample crucible which was attached to a sensitive microbalance assembly.

The sensitivity of the balance was one tenth of a milligram (0.1 mg). The sample holder portion of the TGA balance assembly was subsequently placed inside a high temperature furnace. The heating rate was maintained at 5°C min^{-1} up to the desired temperature (1000°C).

Catalytic activity towards CO oxidation :

The catalysts prepared in this study were tested for the oxidation of CO in air by using a fixed bed laboratory heated by a programmable Lenton tube furnace. The reaction gas containing 1% CO in air was fed to the reactor using mass flow controllers to give a total of approximately 100 $\text{cm}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$. About 50 mg of catalysts was placed in a pyrex tube on a quartz wool plug. A CO_2 sensor (Servomex Analyser Series 1400) was used to analyse the amount of CO_2 in the output gas. The reaction was performed in the temperature range 40–180°C at atmospheric pressure.

The catalyst prepared using acetylacetonate precursor and treated with microwave radiation were not used for these CO oxidation studies due to the fact that the decomposition of the undecomposed precursor produces huge amounts of CO_2 which interferes with CO_2 formed as a result of CO oxidation.

Conclusions :

Comparing the Powder X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) pat-

terns of the catalysts with JCPDS file data identifies the partially crystalline phase of alumina which was evident from the broad nature of the peaks. Pd was present on alumina support as PdO_x whenever it was detected by XRD. The dispersion of metal particles in the catalysts, prepared using nitrate precursor, was not affected significantly by microwave radiation, whereas, in the case of catalysts (2%) prepared using acetylacetonate, an irregular trend in the dispersion values was observed. The range of metal dispersion varied from 14–43%. Temperature Programmed Reduction and Thermo-Gravimetric Analysis showed that microwave radiation didn't completely decompose the acetylacetonate precursor. The catalysts prepared using the nitrate salt was found to lose weight upon heating, which could be due to some moisture present in the catalyst. No phase transformation in alumina was observed. Irradiating the prepared catalysts with microwaves did not seem to affect the performance of the catalysts significantly.

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